

How Does Armed Conflict Influence Population? A Complex Systems Case Study of Nepal

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Abstract

This study examines how armed conflict influences population size and growth. Human population size and change has well-documented importance for human, and environmental well-being worldwide and armed conflicts are unfortunately common. But research has yet to examine if and how conflict might influence population size and growth. It is assumed that increased deaths and out-migration would lead to decreased population size. But armed conflict may also induce population change through fertility and return migration. In this study, we utilize an agent-based model (ABM) to examine the complex and dynamic interplay of population behaviors, including marriage and marital fertility, over a prolonged period of armed conflict. The ABM is situated in Nepal during the 1996–2006 armed conflict and informed by high-quality, representative, and detailed data from the Chitwan Valley Family Study prospective panel survey. Contrary to intuitive assumptions, we find that population size and growth increase dramatically during the armed conflict period. While population growth rates converge to stable and lower levels after the conflict, population size remains higher for decades after the resolution of the conflict. Interrogation of this result shows that this trend is largely caused by dramatic increases in marriage rates and marital fertility rates during the violence.

Keywords: Armed Conflict, Population Growth, Population Size, Agent-based Model

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Introduction

In this study, we investigate if and how armed conflict influences population size and growth. Population size and growth has substantial impacts on almost every aspect of human and environmental well-being globally in the immediate and long-term. Accordingly, understanding and projecting these processes is of substantial importance for local, national, and international policy and programming. This is evidenced by the considerable amount of money and effort spent on censuses by almost all governments around the world, and the great attention to increasing sophistication of population projection methods (Liu and Raftery 2024; Yu et al. 2023; Raftery and Ševčíková 2023).

At the same time, little is known about how armed conflict might influence population size in the immediate term, growth rates in the long term, and how this might be incorporated into population projections, policy, and planning. Armed conflicts might appear rare, given that only a few regularly make front page in international news (like Ukraine and Gaza in the present day). However, careful enumeration of conflicts worldwide shows this phenomenon is, in fact, much more prevalent than we often perceive – 39 countries, for instance, experienced conflicts on their soil in 2022. The combined population of these countries is about 3.7 billion, comprising about 46% of the global population. If we are to include countries with conflicts in the past 10 years, this estimate rises to 52 countries and 73% of the global population (Davies et al. 2023), though these figures should only be seen as approximate given that many conflicts are geographically limited and affect only part of a country’s population. Nonetheless, they offer a rough estimate and indication of the prevalence of armed conflict globally.

These calculations suggest that armed conflict might indeed have substantial impacts on global population size and growth. Yet, to our knowledge, no research to date has analyzed whether this is indeed the case. One reason may be the automatic assumption that population size and growth will decline due to deaths induced by armed conflict. But although armed conflicts cause fatalities, and each death is significant, fatality rates are often fairly low when taken as a percent of the entire population (Levy and Sidel 2016).

Population size and growth are also influenced by other demographic behaviors, such as marriage, fertility, and out- and return-migration. For example, a relatively small decrease in the age at first birth can cause substantial changes to the population growth rate (Tor-

risi 2022). Existing research also suggests that armed conflict influences other demographic behaviors, including marriage, fertility, and migration (Torrise 2022; Torrise 2020; Meertens and Segura-Escobar 1996; Svallfors and Billingsley 2019; Casey and Tshipamba 2017; Kraehnert et al. 2019; McGinn et al. 2011; Rotondi and Rocca 2022; Verwimp et al. 2020; Williams, Dirgha J. Ghimire, et al. 2012; Heuveline and Poch 2007; Jayaraman et al. 2009; Agadjanian and Prata 2002; Conrad et al. 1996; Palloni et al. 1996), which have further implications for population growth. Given that conflict can influence all behaviors contributing to population growth, and these effects unfold dynamically over time, conventional projection approaches – which assume fixed fertility, mortality, and migration rates– are unable to capture the impact of conflict on population size and growth.

This study is an empirical analysis of just this question – how does armed conflict influence population size and growth? We use an agent-based model (ABM) to examine the dynamics of marriage, marital fertility, and migration during armed conflict and their combined influence on population size and growth. Our ABM is situated in rural Nepal during a recent conflict (1996-2006) and the hypothetical ABM population is based on statistical analysis of the detailed longitudinal panel survey data from the Chitwan Valley Family Study (Axinn, Pearce, et al. 1999; Axinn, Barber, et al. 1997).

Contrary to instinctive assumptions, our results indicate that the conflict caused the *civilian population to grow faster during the conflict* and this effect reverberates for years after the conflict ended. While population growth rates returned to stable and lower levels post-conflict, the overall population size remained markedly higher in scenarios where conflict events were more severe. Our analyses allow us to attribute these increased growth rates largely to period-specific increases in marriage and marital fertility during the conflict period, which far outpace population decline through conflict-related fatalities. We conclude with a discussion of how our results from Chitwan Nepal might apply to other settings, and the potential for ABMs to contribute to a better understanding of how armed conflict and other contextual changes might influence population growth and change.

Armed Conflict and Population Change as a Multi-Level Complex System

The nature of our question –how does armed conflict influence population size and growth– is inherently causal and based on an aggregate measure (population size). Yet, this question is difficult to address for several reasons. The first challenge relates to the methodological dif-

ficuity of modeling a population as a complex system, which requires extensive data requirements such as having detailed representative longitudinal panel survey data collected during an armed conflict. The relative lack of such data is likely a key reason for the lack of research to date on this question, despite its significance in understanding global population growth.

Secondly, conventional methods of analysis are inadequate to address the causal nature of this question. For instance, a straightforward way to examine the impact of conflict is by observing population change at the aggregate level between two dates (e.g. the beginning and end of a conflict). However this does not allow for the identification of the cause underlying such population change. Such change may be reflective of population trends occurring even before the conflict (e.g., sustained fertility decline/increase; mortality improvements due to healthcare expansion). Otherwise, many other factors can also change at the same time as a conflict, such as weather disasters, global economic changes, and pandemics. Thus, a straightforward aggregate count of a population does not allow one to isolate the cause of that change.

Additionally, our question is about change in population size and growth, which are quantities at the aggregate or macro-level. Basic demography suggests that such change is caused by individual or micro-level behaviors, such as birth, death, and migration. Common regression procedures can, and have, been used to understand how conflict or other macro-level events influence these micro-level behaviors (Green et al. 2018; Neal et al. 2016). However, straightforward aggregation of micro-level behaviors is not appropriate because micro-level behaviors aggregate in non-linear ways over time. For example, we might expect aggregate marriage rates to increase during periods of armed conflict, because conflict tends to lead to individual-level increases in the likelihood of marriage (Singh et al. 2022). However, conflicts have also been shown to increase migration rates (Williams, O'Brien, et al. 2021), which in turn reduces the likelihood of marriage (Carlson 1985). There are then two opposing influences on aggregate marriage rates: conflict-induced increases in individual marriage likelihood, and migration-influenced decreases in marriage likelihood. This interplay of factors therefore preclude a straightforward aggregation of individual-level behaviors into macro-level demographic change, highlighting the need for approaches that explicitly account for the dynamic and non-linear processes linking micro-level actions to population-level outcomes.

Given this situation, we address our methodological needs by carefully conceptualizing how micro and macro contexts dynamically influence demographic behaviors and aggregate

population size. We conceptualize a population as a group of individuals who undertake an array of individual behaviors (e.g. marriage, fertility, migration). Each individual’s likelihood of undertaking a behavior depends on their characteristics (gender, age, etc.), their statuses (married, migrant, etc.), their meso-context (other household members’ employment, migration, residence, etc.) and their macro-context (armed conflict, pandemic, economic recession, etc.). This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of complex system

Within this framework, individual-level changes in behaviours (e.g., marriage) induced by conflict are accompanied by corresponding changes in statuses at both the individual (e.g., being married) and household level (e.g., shifts in household composition), which in turn affect behaviors at later times (e.g., likelihood to migrate). Accordingly, we can think of population change over time as an iterative series of time steps, as shown in Figure 1. Notice that in the final (or any) time step, one can count up the number of people in the macro population to get the population size and growth.

Methods

Agent-based Modelling

We use an agent-based model (ABM) to model the dynamic interactions between micro, meso, and macro influences on micro-level demographic behaviors, which in turn influence macro-level population size and growth. ABM are computational simulations of a hypothetical population. They allow individuals (agents) to undertake behaviors, like marriage, migration, birth, and death, according to programmed behavioral rules. The behavioral rules can allow for individuals to interact with each other, and the conflict-related events that occur in their

context.

The probability of agents adopting particular behaviors are contingent on their existing states at every time step. For instance, agents only qualify for pregnancy or childbirth if they are not already in a state of pregnancy, are less than 45 years old, and are married and residing with their spouses. Eligible agents then have differential probabilities of pregnancy and childbirth, depending on whether they have given birth before. Within our ABM, the probability of becoming pregnant for women without children is given by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\text{pregnancy} \mid \text{no child}) &= \log\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = -2.1332 \\
 &+ (\text{gun_battles}) * -0.1227 \\
 &+ (\text{bomb_blasts}) * 0.0114 \\
 &+ (\text{education}) * 0.0256 \\
 &+ (\text{age}) * -0.0309
 \end{aligned}$$

Contrarily, the chances of pregnancy for women already with children are different. Compared to the earlier scenario, the probability of pregnancy for those with a single child includes additional factors such as the agent's age at first birth, and the number of girls born:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\text{pregnancy} \mid \text{one child}) &= \log\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = -1.7692 \\
 &+ (\text{gun_battles}) * -0.2497 \\
 &+ (\text{bomb_blasts}) * -0.0176 \\
 &+ (\text{strikes_and_protests}) * -0.5079 \\
 &+ (\text{education}) * 0.00467 \\
 &+ (\text{age}) * -0.1216 \\
 &+ (\text{no. of girls born}) * 0.0938 \\
 &+ (\text{age at first birth}) * 0.0411
 \end{aligned}$$

Our ABM therefore calculates the probability of pregnancy –and indeed, other behaviors– for agents at each time point, depending on their characteristics. These probabilistic behaviors shape not only subsequent behaviors of the same agent, but also the behaviors of other agents at future time points. For instance, having children also decreases the likelihood of subsequent out-migration, and increases the probability of return migration by spouses. By

simulating both intra-personal and interpersonal dynamics between agents and their behaviors, our ABM enables us to capture their non-linear effects on population size. Unlike conventional regression approaches which typically assume linear and stable relationships, our ABM framework captures the recursive interplay between macro-, meso-, and micro-level circumstances and individual behaviours, which in turn collectively shapes population trajectories over time.

Another notable feature of ABMs is their ability to function as experimental sandboxes to simulate counterfactual events that did not happen in the real world. For instance, we can simulate outcomes based on a scenario where armed conflict happened, and another experimental scenario where armed conflict is absent. Resulting differences in output between these two scenarios can then be directly attributed to the presence of armed conflict. Put otherwise, ABMs allow for the direct isolation of ‘treatment effects’ (e.g., levels of armed conflict) that account for the differences in outcomes.

We specify three ‘treatment’ conditions in this study. The first treatment represents a scenario of *No Conflict*, in which we simulated the absence of violent or political events across all time points. The second treatment condition, *Conflict*, replicates the exact number of conflict events as observed in Chitwan District during the period of armed conflict. In this treatment, we included in our ABM the observed number of gun battles, bomb blasts, and other variables related to the armed conflict in every month throughout the simulated time period. The third and final treatment condition represent a level of *Extreme Conflict*, wherein the number of conflict events are simulated to be twice that of the *Conflict* scenario. Because all variables apart from these conflict events are held constant, resulting changes in population sizes may therefore be attributed to differences in treatment conditions.

In line with previous studies, we allowed our ABM to run for 17 years prior to the armed conflict (Williams, O’Brien, et al. 2021). This ‘burn in’ period stabilises our model by allowing children born in the first year of the simulation to age into eligibility for the various demographic behaviors in our model (e.g., marriage and childbirth). This increases our confidence that changes in population size across treatment conditions can indeed be attributed to the conflict, rather than the stabilization process. We re-ran our simulations 500 times for each treatment scenario, and reported the average population size across all time periods.

Setting

Our ABM is based on the population of western Chitwan District in south central Nepal. Chitwan can be generally characterized as an agricultural area, with one large city, surrounded by suburbs and then rural villages. It is home to a variety of ethnic and caste groups that broadly represent the population of Nepal in general. Living standards are reasonably comparable to other rural agricultural based areas in South and Southeast Asia (Agadjanian and Prata 2002; Agadjanian and Prata 2001).

The Chitwan setting is ideal for our purposes for two main reasons. First, there was a moderate intensity armed conflict in Nepal from 1996-2006, which affected Chitwan from 2001-2006. While high intensity conflicts are reported more often in international news, moderate (and mild) intensity conflicts are more common around the world (Davies et al. 2023). The conflict in Chitwan occurred between the Government of Nepal and the Communist Party of Nepal-Maoist, otherwise known as “the Maoists”. Violent events included bombings, gun battles, house raids, assassinations, beatings, and more. Threatening political events included strikes, protests, States of Emergency with martial law, ceasefires, and the assassination of most of the royal family in 2001. Regardless of their association with either side, civilians were affected by these political events and often victims of the violent events as well. Studies using different methods all show that civilians felt continuously threatened throughout the conflict, and that the conflict influenced migration, contraceptive use, marriage, and mental health (Axinn, Dirgha J Ghimire, et al. 2013; Williams 2013; Williams, Dirgha J. Ghimire, et al. 2012).

Data

The second reason that Chitwan is an ideal study setting is that it is the location of the rich and detailed data needed for our analysis. Our population data come from the Chitwan Valley Family Study (CVFS), a survey of over 5,000 people in western Chitwan District (Axinn, Pearce, et al. 1999; Axinn, Barber, et al. 1997). Beginning in 1996 and continuing to date, the survey is a longitudinal panel that records demographic behaviors (including marriage, birth, contraceptive use, and migration) with monthly precision. Because the data were collected before, during, and after armed conflict, the CVFS provides a rare opportunity to examine the observed effects of armed conflict on demographic behaviors. In addition to the

prospective demographic registry, the CVFS contains other detailed data, including an individual interview and life history calendar, household agriculture and consumption surveys, and neighborhood history calendars all collected at multiple time points.

Our information about conflict related events comes from a variety of sources. Violent events, including dates and places, were recorded by the South Asia Terrorism Portal (satp.org). We collected data on political events related to the conflict from news and NGO and government records. All of these data for events in Chitwan District were confirmed by staff of ISER-Nepal.

Results

We simulate population level outcomes under three conflict scenarios: *no conflict*; *conflict*; and the *extreme conflict*. The foremost scenario simulate a counterfactual scenario wherein no conflict has occurred; the second reflects the observed level of conflict in reality; and the third simulates an extreme case where the number of conflict events are doubled relative to reality. Our ABM simulations reveal two key findings that immediately address our primary question in this study.

First, as shown in Figure 2, absolute population size increases during armed conflict (shaded in gray), with the observed increase in population size relating directly to the severity of the conflict. The *no conflict* scenario depicts steady population growth through year 30 of the simulation. In contrast, the *conflict* scenario shows sharp increases in population size, with the *extreme conflict* scenario exhibiting an even steeper growth. Where population size is observed to decrease in the long run across all three scenarios, the precipitous increases in size during the conflict period result in persistently higher population sizes, especially in scenarios where conflict is more severe. By year 50, the population in the *no conflict* scenario is 9,945 people, for the *conflict* scenario 10,211 people, and for the *extreme conflict* scenario it is 10,900 people – approximately 9.6% higher than the *no conflict* scenario.

Second, as shown in Figure 3, population growth rates also increase during the conflict period, only when the population is exposed to the treatment condition (i.e., armed conflict). Relative to the entire simulated time period, population growth rates grow and peak during the conflict period in only the *conflict* and *extreme conflict* scenarios (year 19). This contrasts with the *no conflict* scenario, in which population growth rates steadily decline. Further, population growth rates are also consistently higher in the *extreme conflict* rather than *conflict*

Figure 2: Population size in three conflict scenarios

(and *no conflict*) scenario. These differences in population growth rates can be attributed entirely to the treatment condition (exposure to armed conflict), given that all conflict scenarios are completely identical and differ only in the number of conflict events.

Figure 3: Population growth rates across three conflict scenarios

Reasons for Population Increase During the Nepal Armed Conflict

Marriage and Fertility

In considering the determinants of population growth, our ABM specifies only two parameters through which agents can be added to or removed from the population – births and deaths. Our ABM provides evidence of a direct link between armed conflict and increased births. As

shown in Figure 4, birth rates in the *no conflict* scenario steadily decreased throughout the observation period; whereas the *conflict* and *extreme conflict* scenarios exhibit sharp increases to birth rates. This increase is observed only during the conflict period, with birth rates converging in the long run for all scenarios by year 25, suggesting that armed conflict contributes to elevated fertility. Although migration represents another potential pathway for population change, we incorporate migrants in our ABM as part of the overall population so migration patterns do not alter the population size. Moreover, whether or not migrants are accounted for does not change our conclusions, as the number of migrants residing outside the study area at any time has been shown to not substantially change during the conflict (Williams, O’Brien, et al. 2021).

Figure 4: Birth rates across three conflict scenarios

In considering the demographic drivers of such increased birth rates, our ABM model allows for two distinct pathways that can affect childbirth. The first is the *birth probability* equation, which is a regression equation that calculates the probability that a married woman will get pregnant at any time step, contingent on a variety of individual characteristics (e.g., education level) and the number of conflict-related events. We describe this equation in greater detail within the Supplementary Materials Section S1.2. More pertinently, the second way in which birth rates can change is through *childbirth eligibility*. Within our ABM, women are only eligible to get pregnant if they are married, consistent with prevailing social norms around marriage and childbearing observed in Nepal (Williams, Dirgha J. Ghimire, et al. 2012). Marriage rates therefore serve as an important consideration to explain the observed spikes in birth rates during the conflict period.

Similar to birth rates, we find that armed conflict increased marriage rates. As shown in Figure 5, marriage rates for both women (upper) and men (lower) are significantly higher during the conflict period compared to the post-conflict period. They also increase in tandem with the severity of armed conflict, with the *extreme conflict* scenario exhibiting the highest rates of marriage. These increased marriage rates create a greater proportion of people who are eligible for childbirth in the conflict scenarios, potentially contributing to elevated birth rates. Indeed, Figure 5 shows that spikes in marriage rates precede peaks in childbirth (indicated by vertical lines) by exactly one year for both the men and women. For instance, where male and female marriage rates peak at years 18 and 22 of the simulation, we observe that birth and population growth rates peak at years 19 and 23 respectively. This correspondence suggests a pattern where marriage positively predicts increased birth rates. Ostensibly, increased marriage rates during the armed conflict contribute to heightened birth rates during armed conflict, thus accounting partially for increased population growth and overall higher population size.

In explicating childbirth as a key component of population growth, we considered whether the observed increase in birth rates is driven primarily by the direct influence of armed conflict on fertility behaviour (as captured by our birth regression equation), or indirectly through changes in marriage rates induced by conflict. In the latter case where heightened birth rates are caused by increases in marriage, we would expect changes in birth rates to closely track marriage rates. In contrast, if birth rates are mediated solely or primarily by the birth equation, then we would expect an inconsistent relationship between marriage and birth rates.

Overlaying female marriage rates over birth rates, we find that both processes contribute to increased birth rates. As shown in Figure 6, peaks in birth rates at years 19 and 23 closely follow increases in marriage rates a year earlier (years 18 and 22), suggesting that rising birth rates during armed conflict are partially driven by increased marriage rates. At the same time, inconsistencies in the magnitude of change between female marriage and birth rates also suggest the direct influence of armed conflict on the likelihood of childbirth. Specifically, individuals are more likely to have children in the presence, rather than the absence, of armed conflict. This is illustrated by the disproportionate relationship between marriage and birth rates observed during the conflict period relative to the post-conflict period: where a small increase in female marriage rates during years 18-19 precipitates a large increase in birth rates *during* the conflict period, a larger increase in marriage rates between years 21 to 22 is fol-

Figure 5: Female and male marriage rates across three conflict scenarios

lowed by only a markedly smaller rise in birth rates *after* the conflict period. This suggests that the probability of birth is substantially higher during the conflict period, resulting in elevated birth rates despite only modest changes in marriage rates.

Taking these observations together, we can conclude that the armed conflict contributes to an increased number of married women eligible for childbirth, and a greater probability of birth per woman during the conflict period. Together, these influence the overall sharp increases in birth rates, which account for the increase in population size during the armed conflict.

Figure 6: Comparison of female marriage and birth rates

Death

Mortality constitutes another component affecting population size. Our ABM allows for the possibility of death at any time step through a regression equation and probabilistic determination, similar to the process for marriage and pregnancy. However, the death equation does not allow conflict events to influence the probability of death, which more accurately reflect mortality patterns during the moderately intense armed conflict in Nepal. While the actual conflict substantially affected daily life, including marriage and fertility decisions (Neal et al. 2016; Devkota and Teijlingen 2010), the death rate was comparatively low. The Annual Human Rights Yearbooks estimate 258 deaths due directly to the conflict (Informal Service Sector 2025), corresponding to a death rate of 0.05% of the 472,048 population of Chitwan District. Applying this death rate to our ABM population yields 5.6 estimated conflict-related fatalities over the five-year conflict period, which are too few to reliably estimate the influence of armed conflict on the probability of death using a regression equation.

To account for conflict-related mortality in our ABM, we apply direct accounting. In our model, the *no conflict* scenario resulted in 10,660 people by year 22 at the end of the conflict, the *conflict* scenario resulted in 10,905 people, and *extreme conflict* 11,386 people. Subtracting the estimated fatalities (six fatalities for the *conflict* scenario; 20 for the *extreme conflict*) from our model estimates do not alter our primary conclusions: armed conflict resulted in higher population size in both the immediate and long-term, due to substantially greater population growth rates during the conflict, which are in turn caused by elevated rates of mar-

riage and fertility during the conflict period.

Discussion and Conclusion

We return to our original question outlined at the start of the article: does armed conflict influence population size and growth? Our findings suggest a counter-intuitive pattern that armed conflict in Chitwan Nepal has led to increases in population size both during, and persisting after the conflict period. We investigated the mechanisms of such population dynamics and found increased birth rates to be a primary driver of this population growth, which outweigh the slight increases in conflict-related deaths. Higher birth rates are in turn caused by a combination of higher marriage rates and higher rates of marital birth.

Marriage and birth rates might increase during armed conflict for several reasons. First, accelerated marriage serves as a protective factor for males and females during armed conflict. Civilians are at a heightened risk of being abducted into military factions during armed conflict, where they often suffer prolonged sexual violence (Park 2011). Unmarried women in particular, are six times as likely to experience sexual slavery compared to women who were married, abandoned, or widowed (Bartels et al. 2010). Young married women are also less likely to be abducted during armed raids on villages compared to their unmarried counterparts (Stavrou 2011). Similarly, unmarried males also served as primary targets of forced conscription, due to their comparative lack of family obligations and susceptibility towards radical ideologies (Williams, Dirgha J. Ghimire, et al. 2012). Marrying during periods of armed conflict therefore serves as a protective strategy to mitigate against the threat of forced conscription.

Second, periods of armed conflict may elevate unmet healthcare needs, due to the disruption of medical and contraceptive supplies. Healthcare and contraceptive supplies to health centres, for instance, may be intercepted by Maoist rebels or disrupted by strikes (Williams, Dirgha J. Ghimire, et al. 2012; Brauner-Otto et al. 2007), undermining individuals' ability to regulate family planning. Armed conflict may also inflate desired family size, which is often cited as a coping strategy to replace family members lost in conflict (Urdal and Che 2013). The availability of healthcare staff and health infrastructures may also be adversely impacted, leading to expectations of heightened infant mortality (Abouharb 2023; Lindskog 2016). Such expectations may in turn translate to an increased tempo and quantum of childbirth as a compensatory strategy to ensure that some offspring survive into adulthood (Kirk and Pillet

1998).

While the results of this study apply specifically to the western Chitwan region of Nepal, our interrogation of the possible mechanisms helps us to understand how these results can be adapted to other populations experiencing armed conflicts. We argue that other contexts need only exhibit certain traits to adopt similar population trajectories as our findings illustrate. Specifically, contexts where marriage serves as a protective factor (e.g., against military violence and exploitation) may be inclined to marry and give birth earlier, precipitating a trajectory of population growth. We anticipate such a trend to be more apparent especially among populations with unmet contraceptive needs, given the substantial disruptions to health and medical supplies during armed conflict.

Beyond our findings about the population size of Chitwan during the armed conflict, we also reiterate here the merits of adopting ABMs in demographic research. As our study demonstrates, using an ABM approach allowed us to simulate counterfactual experimental scenarios (i.e., the *no conflict* and *extreme conflict* scenarios) to isolate the causal effect of armed conflict on population size. It also allows us to demonstrate the non-linear relationship between the severity of armed conflict and demographic outcomes. This is best illustrated by how the doubling of conflict events in the *extreme conflict* scenario does not translate correspondingly to an exact doubling of marriage, fertility, or population growth rates in the actual *conflict* scenario. This is because agents in our ABMs, like people within real populations, possess varying statuses (e.g., their level of education; marital status) and are thus differentially influenced by armed conflict. By accounting for how demographic statuses change after demographic behaviors that occur over time, as conflicts occur over time, we are then able to simulate the complex interactions of the population with their context. Hence, a doubling of armed conflict events in our model does not translate to a subsequently doubled increase in marriage or childbirth. This deviates from a regression approach where demographic outcomes across the population are treated as a linear function of armed conflict events, and which do not reflect how actual populations react to armed conflict. Thus, ABMs are a powerful tool for future research to examine the complex and non-linear influences of armed conflicts and other contextual changes on the fundamental output of demography—population growth and change.

Data Availability

The CVFS dataset can be accessed at no cost through the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) platform. Detailed information on how to access and utilize the data can also be found on its main website (cvfs.isr.umich.edu/data/data-access/data-access-instructions/).

Additional Information

Supplementary Information is available for this paper.

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Supplementary Information

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This file contains supplementary material for the agent-based model (ABM) utilised in “How Does Armed Conflict Influence Population? A Complex Systems Case Study of Nepal”. It is meant as a reference for readers to understand the ‘decision rules’ adopted by agents within the ABM when simulated across the various conflict scenarios within our study.

S1: Behavioural rules for Chitwan agent-based model (individual level)

S1.1: MARRIAGE

The conditions of being eligible for marriage in the ABM are agents who are:

- not married
- at least 14 years old
- resident in Chitwan neighborhood (ie not a migrant)

The following regression equations reflect the probability of getting married for men and women respectively.

Probability of Marriage – Men

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log (P/(1-P))} &= (-7.3314) \\ &+ (\text{gun_battles} * 0.3281) \\ &+ (\text{emergency} * 0.6211) \\ &+ (\text{instability} * 0.2576) \\ &+ (\text{strikes_and_protests} * 0.7903) \\ &+ (\text{age} * 0.1244) \\ &+ (\text{education} * (-0.0253)) \\ &+ (\text{high_caste} * (-0.2122)) \\ &+ (\text{ever_migrated_outside_Nepal} * 0.3681) \\ &+ (\text{nbh_organizations} * 0.0358) \\ &+ (\text{distance} * 0.0345) \end{aligned}$$

Probability of Marriage – Women

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log (P/(1-P))} &= (-4.9742) \\ &+ (\text{gun_battles} * 0.3624) \\ &+ (\text{bomb_blasts} * (-0.0664)) \\ &+ (\text{emergency} * 0.2403) \\ &+ (\text{instability} * 0.4063) \\ &+ (\text{age} * 0.0053) \\ &+ (\text{education} * 0.0385) \\ &+ (\text{high_caste} * 0) \\ &+ (\text{distance} * 0.0437) \end{aligned}$$

S1.2: PREGNANCY AND BIRTH

The conditions of being eligible for pregnancies and childbirth in the ABM are agents who are:

- woman
- married
- living with spouse this month
- not already pregnant
- didn't give birth in the last 4 months
- less than 45 years old.

The following regression equations reflect the probability of getting pregnant and giving birth for women with respective parities:

Probability of Getting pregnant – Women with 0 children

$$\mathbf{Log(P/(1-P)) = (-2.1332)}$$

- + (gun_battles * (-0.1227))
- + (bomb_blasts * (0.0114))
- + (strikes_and_protests * (-0.2367))
- + (education * (0.0256))
- + (age * (-0.0309))

Probability of Getting pregnant – Women with 1 child

$$\mathbf{Log(P/(1-P)) = (-1.7692)}$$

- + (gun_battles * (-0.2497))
- + (bomb_blasts * (-0.0176))
- + (strikes_and_protests * (-0.5079))
- + (education * (0.00467))
- + (age * (-0.1216))
- + (# of girls ever born * (0.0938))
- + (age at first birth * (0.0411))

Probability of Getting pregnant – Women with 2 or more children

$$\mathbf{Log(P/(1-P)) = (-2.3443)}$$

- + (gun_battles * (0.1943))
- + (bomb_blasts * (-0.1431))
- + (strikes_and_protests * (0.2872))
- + (education * (-0.1166))
- + (age * (-0.1778))
- + (# of girls ever born * (0.4941))
- + (# of children ever born * (-0.3439))
- + (age at first birth * (0.1867))
- + (- 0.3924) (if household in middle third of assets distribution last year)
- + (-0.7760) (if household in top third of assets distribution last year)

Giving birth

If a woman gets pregnant, set birth month = month of pregnancy + 9

S1.3 DEATH:

All individuals are eligible for death within the ABM.

The following regression equations reflect the probability of death for men and women respectively:

Initial Probability of Death- Men

$$\text{Log (P/(1-P))} = (-9.9579)$$

$$+ (\text{age} * 0.0410)$$

$$+ (\text{age squared} * 0.000268)$$

Initial Probability of Death- Women

$$\text{Log (P/(1-P))} = (-9.4241)$$

$$+ (\text{age} * -.0179)$$

$$+ (\text{age squared} * 0.00111)$$

$$\text{Probability of death} = \text{initial probability of death} * 2$$

S1.4: EDUCATION

Education target

Set education target at birth.

ed_target = education of parent of same sex + 2 years

Maximum limit of 16 years on *ed_target*.

Enrollment

If education equals education target, then enroll = 0.

If education is less than education target and agent was enrolled during the last month of last year, and total educational attainment is <16 years then enroll=1.

S1.5: OUT MIGRATION- ADULTS

The conditions of being eligible for out-migration in the ABM are agents who are:

- at least 16 years old
- less than 50 years old

The following regression equations reflect the probability of out-migration for men and women respectively:

Probability of Out-migration- Men

Log (P/(1-P)) = (-8.1087)

- + (gun_battles * (0.1198))
- + (bomb_blasts * (-0.0113))
- + (emergency * (-0.1621))
- + (instability * (0.6995))
- + (strikes_and_protests * (-0.2442))
- + (gun_battles*salary * (-0.1905))
- + (gun_battles*ln_land * 0.0676)
- + (bomb_blasts*married_living_with_spouse * 0.0420)
- + (bomb_blasts*married_apart * (0.00633))
- + (emergency*high_caste * (-0.1259))
- + (emergency*married_living_with_spouse * 0.0879)
- + (emergency*kids * 0.0271)
- + (emergency*salary * (- 0.0338))
- + (instability*high_caste * (-0.1900))
- + (instability*married_living_with_spouse * (-0.4934))
- + (instability*kids * 0.0753)
- + (instability*salary * (-0.0526))
- + (instability*distance * (-0.0387))
- + (strikes_and_protests*nbh_organizations * 0.1088)
- + (age * (-0.0376))
- + (high_caste * (-0.2274))
- + (education * 0.0190)
- + (married_living_with_spouse * (0.0542))
- + (married_living_apart * (-1.3707))
- + (widowed * 0.4328)
- + (kids * -0.0103)
- + (salary * 0.3212)
- + (ln_land * (0.0283))
- + (-0.1133) (if household in bottom third of asset distribution last year)
- + (0.2791) (if household in bottom third of income distribution last year)
- + (0.2006) (if household in middle third of income distribution last year)
- + (distance * 0.0291)
- + (nbh_organizations * (-0.0589))
- + (ln_nbh_percent_migrants * 1.1182)

+ (ever_migrated_before_start * 0.2058)
 + (migrations_since_start * 0.3485)
 + (months_back * 0.00203)
 + (months_away * 0.0292)
 + (july * (-0.2850))
 + (august * 0.2402)
 + (september * 0.0594)
 + (october * (-0.5058))

Probability of Out-migration- Women

Log (P/(1-P)) = (-6.1906)

+ (gun_battles * (0.2876))
 + (bomb_blasts * (-0.0796))
 + (emergency * (0.0304))
 + (instability * 0.2981)
 + (strikes_and_protests * (-0.8163))
 + (gun_battles*education * (-0.00444))
 + (gun_battles*ln_land * 0.0883)
 + (gun_battles*nbh_organizations * (-0.1561))
 + (bomb_blasts*married_living_with_spouse * 0.1178)
 + (bomb_blasts*married_living_apart * 0.1031)
 + (bomb_blasts*kids * (-0.00108))
 + (emergency*kids * 0.0108)
 + (instability*high_caste * (-0.3164))
 + (instability*married_living_apart * (0.000481))
 + (instability*kids * (-0.0115))
 + (instability*distance * (-0.0166))
 + (strikes_and_protests*high_caste * 0.6881)
 + (strikes_and_protests*education * (-0.0340))
 + (strikes_and_protests*kids * 0.1643)
 + (strikes_and_protests*ln_land * (-0.2210))
 + (age * (0.00113))
 + (high_caste * ((-0.1593))
 + (education * 0.0398)
 + (married_living_with_spouse * (-0.0330))
 + (married_living_apart * 0.7557)
 + (widowed * 0.7516)
 + (kids * (-0.0438))
 + (salary * (-0.0584))
 + (ln_land * 0.0384)
 + (distance * (-0.0220))
 + (nbh_organizations * 0.0646)
 + (ln_nbh_percent_migrants * 0.8707)
 + (ever_migrated_before_start * 0.00884)
 + (migrations_since_start * 0.2700)

+ (months_back * (-0.0227))
+ (months_away * (-0.00067))
+ (july * (-0.4299))
+ (october * (-0.1839))

Note: nbh_percent_migrants (the percentage of neighborhood residents who were migrants last month) will be calculated by the model. However, since the data starts with all agents resident in the neighborhood- for the first 12 months of the model, input the average percent migrants for each neighborhood for months 12-23.

S1.6: OUT MIGRATION- CHILDREN (DEPENDENTS)

The conditions of being eligible for out-migration among children (dependents) in the ABM are agents who are:

- less than 16 years old
- both parents are currently migrants
- at least one parent is in South Asia or Nepal region.

The probability of out-migration for girls and boys is 0.50. If child migrates, then he/she will go to South Asia or Nepal region.

Note: this means that for each month, adults migration behaviors must be run first. Then children's migrations depend on their adult parents' behaviors.

Migration Updates:

- If agent migrates and salary is 1, then set salary to 0 (i.e. they leave their salaried job if they migrate).
- If agent migrates and enroll is 1, then set enroll to 0 (i.e. they leave school if they migrate).

S2: Behavioural rules for Chitwan agent-based model (household level)

Households are defined as a group of people living together in the same house. The model is designed so that they are always family and no non-family members are allowed to live in a household.

For the purposes of the model, a household is defined by the oldest person and their spouse. For tracking land, assets, debt, and income, the oldest person and their spouse own all of these items until they are split. Other household members can contribute to the household income, debt, and assets with the equations below. If the oldest person in the household dies, for tracking purposes, the land, assets, debt, and income will be transferred to their spouse. If the spouse dies, follow the rules below for inheritance for land and assets. If the spouse dies, the debt account disappears, it is not inherited.

Households can do the following ‘behaviors’

- Earn income
- Increase assets
- ~~Take on debt~~
- Die and bequeath – upon death of
- Split
- Start a new household (after splitting)
- Purchase land
- Purchase livestock
- Purchase a house

Sub-families are defined by a married son, with or without kids. Once a married son and his wife are a sub-family, they are always a sub-family. If the married son or his wife dies, the remaining spouse and their kids (if they have kids) are still a sub-family.

S2.1: ASSETS AND INCOME

Income is calculated at the end of each year (the last month of the year).

The following regression equation reflect the income for households at the end of the year:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Income} = & (7000 * \# \text{ of person months of salaried job worked by all household members}) \\ & + (800 * \text{khet_owned}) \\ & + (400 * \text{khet_rented}) \\ & + (600 * \text{bari_owned}) \\ & + (300 * \text{bari_rented}) \\ & + (150 * \# \text{ of poultry}) \\ & + (5,000 * \# \text{ of buffaloes}) \\ & + (5000 * \# \text{ of cows}) \\ & + (1000 * \# \text{ of pigs}) \\ & + (1000 * \# \text{ of goats}) \\ & + (8000 * \text{hh_months_international_migration_last_year}) \\ & + (4,000 * \text{hh_months_domestic_migration_last_year}) \\ & - (3750 * \# \text{ of people in household}) \\ & - (75,000 * \# \text{ hh members who migrated to any region besides South Asia or Nepal}) \\ & - (3000 * \# \text{ hh members who migrated to South Asia or Nepal}) \\ & - (55,000 * \# \text{ of kattha of khet land bought this year}) \\ & - (55,000 * \# \text{ of kattha of bari land bought this year}) \\ & - (25 * \# \text{ of chickens bought this year}) \\ & - (10,000 * \# \text{ of buffaloes bought this year}) \\ & - (25,000 * \# \text{ of cows bought this year}) \\ & - (1000 * \# \text{ of pigs bought this year}) \\ & - (1000 * \# \text{ of goats bought this year}) \end{aligned}$$

Assets are calculated at the end of each year (the last month of the year)

The following regression equation reflect the assets of households at the end of the year:

$$\text{Assets} = \text{assets last year} + \text{income this year}$$

Notes:

The units for income and assets are Nepali rupees.

S2.2: HOUSEHOLD SPLIT

The conditions of being eligible for household splits in the ABM are:

- if there are 2 or more sub-families, then the oldest sub-family is eligible to move out.

The following regression equation reflect the probability for household splits:

Probability of moving out = 0.70

+ (0.10 * husband has a salaried job)

+ (0.10 * wife has a salaried job)

+ (0.10 * # of kids in the sub-family)

- If there is one sub-family:

- o If it is the youngest son, then

Probability of moving out = 0

- o If it is not the youngest son, then

Probability of moving out = 0.20

+ (0.10 * husband has a salaried job)

+ (0.10 * wife has a salaried job)

+ (0.10 * # of kids in the sub-family)

S2.3: INHERITANCE

The following conditions reflect the distribution of inheritance within the household.

S2.3.1: Assets

- When a daughter gets married, the household gives 15% of their assets to her.
- When the first sub-family (married son) moves out of a household, then the household assets are split into S+1 shares, where S is the number of sons living in the household (including the one that is moving out. The +1 is to create a share for the parents to keep.
- The son who moves out gets one share. The remaining shares remain in the household.
- When the next son moves out, the S+1 shares of assets are recalculated at that time. Each share might have a different amount than when the last son moved out, because the household might have added or lost money since that time.
- If there are no sons, then assets get split evenly between daughters (D+1 shares).
- If there are no children, then assets are given to another relative. In this case, the assets just disappear from the ABM.

S2.3.2: Land

- If total land owned is less than or equal to 0.00 kattha, then:
 - o All land goes to the oldest son.
 - o If there are no sons, then all land goes to the oldest daughter.
 - o If there are no sons or daughters, then the land is given to another relative and disappears from the ABM.** Note: This is just a place holder to use in case land gets too fragmented. If land gets too fragmented, then I can increase the threshold of 0.00 kattha to a realistic amount of land.
- If total land owned is more than 0.00 kattha then land is split similarly to assets:
 - o When the first sub-family (married son) moves out of a household, then the household land is split into S+1 shares, where S is the number of sons living in the household (including the one that is moving out. The +1 is to create a share for the parents to keep.
 - o The son who moves out gets one share. The remaining shares remain in the household.
 - o If the household owns bari and khet land, then bari land is split evenly and khet land is split evenly, so each son gets the same amount of each kind of land.
 - o If there are no sons, then the bari and khet land will be split evenly between daughters (D+1 shares).
 - o If there are no children, then land will be given to another relative and disappears from the ABM.

S2.3.3: Parents death

When the last parent dies,

- If there are sons left in the household, then all the parents' remaining land and assets get split evenly between the remaining sons.
 - This applies to sons who are in the household and living there and sons who are in the household but migrants (so they're not living there). It does not apply to sons who have married and then split from the household already.
- If there are no sons, then the remaining share of household land and assets goes to the youngest daughter.
- If parents die and there are more than one unmarried sons in the household, then the remaining unmarried sons will be grouped into one sub-family.

S2.4: START A NEW HOUSEHOLD

When a sub-family moves out of the groom's parents' house, they start their own household.

- They will have the land and assets that they received through inheritance from their parents' household.
- They will buy more land and livestock to reach their allotted amount of each. If they have to go into debt (have negative assets) to do this, that is ok.
- They will rent a house.

** Note: The amounts of 0 and 7 kattha are the median amount of land farmed (including owned and rented) in the 1997 survey which is the beginning of the ABM.

S2.5: PURCHASE LAND AND LIVESTOCK

When a sub-family splits from their parent household, they will immediately (that year) to buy land and livestock in addition to the land they are given.

- When a sub-family splits, calculate the amount of land they will have.
 - o Use the distribution of amount of land owned by households. This is in the document “Distribution of land and livestock, by caste.xls). Randomly choose an amount of land based on this distribution.
 - o There will be different distributions for high caste and low caste. If the new household is high caste, choose the amount of land from the high caste distribution. If the new household is low caste, choose the amount of land from the low caste distribution.
- Calculate the amount of land they will buy.
 - o $\text{Amount of land to buy} = \text{Amount of land they will have} - \text{amount of land they already inherited}.$
- Charge them for buying these items in the income equation. They will only be charged the year that they buy the land and livestock. After that, no charge.

When a sub-family splits into their own household, do this same rule for

- Khet land
- Bari land
- Poultry
- Buffaloes
- Cows
- Pigs
- Goats

New households will not inherit animals from their parent households. So the animals that a new household will ‘have’, they will have to buy them all.